

CLOSED FORM PREDICTIONS OF MACROSCOPIC THERMOMECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ORTHOGONAL 3-D WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: A simple mechanical model for describing elastic moduli and coefficients of thermal expansion of composites using orthogonal 3-D woven fabric reinforcement is proposed in the present work based on the constituent material properties. The theoretical procedure consists of two phases: the first phase is a property description of unidirectional composites as the element of 3-D fabric composites and the second is a description of the whole. Although the emphasis is placed on the second phase, simple but expedient closed form formulae are also developed for predicting E_T and G_{LT} . The second phase is constructed by combination of parallel and serial linkage of the UD composite blocks. The predicted elastic modulus, in-plane shear modulus and coefficient of thermal expansion of Tyranno[®]/epoxy 3-D composite system were compared with experimental results and numerical results obtained from homogenization finite element analysis. An agreement between them are basically excellent. A simple method to predict elastic and thermal expansion behavior of 3-D composites is established.

KEYWORDS: mechanical modeling, serial and parallel linkage, elastic modulus, coefficient of thermal expansion, experiments, homogenization finite element

INTRODUCTION

Three dimensional woven fabric composites have attracted an engineering interest of composite community in recent years. They can provide higher translaminal properties, and imply a potential of low-cost processing of polymer composite structures. Another role of 3-D fabric composites is a reinforcement of ceramic matrix composites (CMC) including carbon/carbon materials. In these composites, because matrices are brittle, functions of translaminal (z) yarns are enhanced. However, such z yarns make gaps between load carrying in-plane (x and y) yarns and deteriorates in-plane mechanical properties. According to this background, simple prediction formulae of mechanical properties of 3-D woven composites are needed more strongly than before in order to establish a quick loop of optimization in material design. Literature survey revealed that no simple closed form formulae had not been proposed yet for description of elastic moduli and coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of

3-D woven composites although some pioneering research work (e.g.: Ref.. 1, 2, 3 and 4) had been conducted.

The purpose of the present paper is first to establish a simple mechanical modeling for description of thermomechanical behavior of orthogonal 3-D fabric composites, and secondly to provide simple full closed form equations for predicting the above-mentioned constants based on the established model. In order to comprehend the structure of the problem at a glance, Table 1 is provided here. Required baseline inputs are constituent material properties of 3-D composites, i. e., Young's moduli, Poisson's ratios, coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of fiber and matrix, fiber volume fraction, and geometrical parameters of 3-D fabrics. Theoretical procedures are divided into two phases; the first phase consists of a prediction of properties of unidirectional (UD) composites as a component of a unit cell of 3-D fabric, and the second phase consists of a prediction of 3-D fabric composite properties based on the established model. For the first phase, a simple and useful closed formula based on a similar mechanical concept to the second phase is proposed, which is another focal point of the present paper. A reliability of this formula was checked by using previous semi-numerical method⁵⁾ developed by one of the author (TI). The second phase procedures are constructed by combinations of parallel and serial linkage of the constituent blocks.

The calculated results through closed form paths were compared with numerical results by homogenization finite element analysis (HFEA). They were also compared with the corresponding experimental results for Tyranno[®]/Epoxy 3-D fabric composites. Agreements of the closed form results with HFEA results and experimental values will be shown to be very good in general.

Table 1 Explanation for Construction of the Theoretical Procedure

Phase for Prediction of UD-Composites

Required Data: $E_f, \nu_f, (G_f), \alpha_f, E_m, \nu_m, (G_m), \alpha_m$

Fiber Volume Fraction in UD; V_{FU}

Methods: Closed Form Formula in Sec. 2 or Ref.5

Outputs: $E_L, E_T, \nu_L, G_{LT}, G_{TT}, (\nu_{TT}), \alpha_L, \alpha_T$

Phase for Prediction of 3-D Fabric Composites

Model Concept and Geometry of 3-D Fabric Composites

Required Data: above outputs and Width of Yarn, b_T &

b_F

Methods: Two Approx. Formulae, PSA & SPA in Sec.3

Outputs: $E_{X1}, G_{XY1}, \alpha_{X1}$ for PSA solution, etc.

PREDICTION OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES FOR UD COMPOSITES

This sort of problems were concern of the early time composite mechanics research and hundreds of papers were published, which were reviewed in, e.g., Ref.6. Of course, there is no problem to predict longitudinal modulus and CTE, E_L and α_L , and major Poisson's ratio, ν_L . Transverse properties like modulus and CTE, E_T, ν_{TT} and α_T , and longitudinal shear modulus G_{LT} were considered to be difficult at first. After cumulative research work, composite community regards these problems as almost solved until some time in 1970's except for the corresponding part to random fiber packing. Some famous formulae like Halpin & Tsai⁷⁾ are quoted in student textbooks. However, it should still be noted that many of those formulae require some semi-empirical factors like contiguity, C. This sort of factors always cause an ambiguity at application. One of the authors (TI) also proposed a semi-numerical method⁵⁾ based on a combination of Fourier expansion of stress functions and point collocation. Its results could be regarded as very close to the exact solution because of an

excellent agreement with preceding numerical analysis and because some mathematical conditions about symmetry were satisfied. One disadvantage of this method was that no closed form expression was obtained. Thus, there remain a necessity for the simplest closed-form formula for predicting particularly E_T and G_{LT} . However, an expediency will be imposed as a penalty of the simplicity.

A sectional geometry of the conceived model at this phase is shown in Fig. 2. According to Ref.5, the hexagonal fiber packing is selected here. One bold simplification introduced here is to employ the hexagonal fiber section. This assumption makes the solution very simple. Note that fiber volume fraction in UD(V_{fu}) is given by $(a/b)^2$. Let us consider the case where $1/2 < b/a < 1$ corresponding to V_{fu} over 25% and where $0 < T_1/b < 1 - a/b$, in the left region. It is assumed that the model is subjected to the tensile force in the T_2 direction and that so-called mechanics of materials approach is adopted after early References of 8 and 9. If the model is cut along the force direction with a width of dT_1 and the force uniformity is assumed, then the modulus in the T_2 direction is obtained as follows using the position of fiber edge $F(T_1)$:

$$E_{T2} = E_f E_m / \{E_m F(T_1) / \sqrt{3} b + E_f (1 - F(T_1)) / \sqrt{3} b\} \quad (1)$$

Because the fiber edge is a slant straight line, Equation 1 can be modified into the following form:

$$E_{T2} = E_f E_m / \{E_m (2a/3b - T_1/3b) + E_f (1 - 2a/3b + T_1/3b)\} \quad (2)$$

In the region where $1 - a/b < T_1/b < 1/2$, one expedient assumption is introduced. Although the true distance of two fibers is $4(a-b) / \sqrt{3}$, it is assumed to be half in order to account stress concentration. If we admit this assumption, E_{T2} becomes constants in this region as follows:

$$E_{T2} = E_f E_m / \{E_m (1/3 + 2a/3b) + E_f (2/3 - 2a/3b)\} \quad (3)$$

If we do not introduce such an expediency, the results are always smaller than the calculated results by the method of Ref.5. In other words, the above distance reduction is considered to be one empirical parameter by which the results can be adjusted to fit the exact solutions. The averaged E_{T2} , namely aimed value of E_T , can be obtained by integrating these equations in the T_1 direction and divided by $b/2$, leading to the following natural logarithmic function :

$$E_T = 6 E_f E_m / (E_f - E_m) \propto n [(E_f - E_m)(1 - a/b) / \{3E_f - 2a/b(E_f - E_m)\} + 1] + 3 E_f E_m (2a/b - 1) / \{E_m (1 + 2a/b) + 2E_f (1 - a/b)\} \quad (4)$$

The second expedient compromise have to be introduced next: The distance reduction truly means an increase of fiber area, which is written in the following form of V_{fu} change:

$$dV_{fu} = 4/3 (1 - a/b)(1 - 1/2/(a/b)) \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1: Model for UD Prediction Phase

Fig. 2: Comparison in predictions of E_T in unidirectional composite phase

However, this V_{fu} change should be neglected, in other words, the initial $V_{fu} = (a/b)^2$ is assumed to be maintained. Otherwise, the results do not coincide with the exact solution curves. According to these strong assumptions, the present solution is regarded as expedient.

The calculated curves based on Eq. 4 are shown in Fig.2 for three cases of composite, Tyranno®/Epoxy, glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy. As it is well known, former two fibers are isotropic and the last is anisotropic. For carbon/epoxy case, E_f is assumed as $E_{fT} = \kappa E_{fL}$ where κ is an anisotropic factor of carbon fiber and where E_{fL} is a longitudinal modulus of carbon fiber.

The used material values are : $E_f = 185\text{GPa}$ for Tyranno®, $E_f = 68.6\text{GPa}$ for glass and $E_{fL} = 187\text{GPa}$ and $\kappa = 0.084$ for carbon fibers. For isotropic fibers, agreements of the present results with exact solutions are fairly good particularly in practical V_{fu} regions. For carbon/epoxy, an agreement becomes slightly worse. Although a description is omitted here, similar equations for G_{LT} and calculated results were obtained. Comparison indicates that the prediction by the closed formula is getting worse than E_T . However, it could be still used if we consider the fact that the hexagonal array provides slightly lower prediction than reality for UD composites due to random fiber packing. Thus, the present formulae are correlated with exact solutions with confidence. We can use them in 45 to 65% V_{fu} if we admit a few percent errors. To meet a need in the next section, E_T of Tyranno®/ Epoxy with $V_{fu} = 59.7\%$, and above material values was determined as 14.1GPa , where exact solution provides 13.9GPa . E_L and ν_L were obtained as 112GPa and 0.26 upon $\nu_m=0.38$ and $\nu_f = 0.2$.

PREDICTION OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES FOR 3-D FABRIC COMPOSITES

Let us proceed into the aimed phase, prediction of mechanical properties of orthogonal 3-D fabric composites. The first step is to establish a mechanical model. Figure 1 depicts the geometry of the model constructed upon micro-observation of an actual composite piece. The model is based on a possible repeating unit cell. Transparent volume denotes regions filled with pure matrix materials. Other regions consist of unidirectional (UD) composite bricks, namely 12 elements in total. Thickness, h_f , and width of yarns, b_F , of fill and warp are assumed to be identical in this model. Width of translaminar (z) yarns is denoted by b_T . Thus, a relationship between local volume fraction in UDC, V_{fu} , and total volume fraction of 3-D composites, V_{fT} , can be written as follows considering pure matrix regions:

$$V_{fT} = V_{fu} \{ (b_F + b_T) b_F + b_T^2 / 2 \} / (b_F + b_T)^2 \quad (6)$$

Actual values of b_F and b_T for the present SCL type orthogonal Tyranno®/Epoxy were measured to be 1.043 and 0.5153 mm respectively. Then, the factor for V_{fu} would be 0.724 . The same epoxy resin with $E_m = 3.43\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_m=0.38$ as UDC, Epicote 828, is used. As stated in the previous section, baseline UDC material properties were already obtained.

Fig.3: Schematic of the mechanical modeling

It is assumed that voids which are inevitable factor in ceramic matrix composites exist only in pure matrix regions. However, since this paper treats only polymer matrix composites, an effect of voids is neglected according to a sectional observation as void free.

Hereafter, we go into the core of the present procedure, development of closed-form formulae for 3-D composite phase. The first one is referred to as the Parallel-Serial approach (PSA) where the parallel volume average of rule of mixture (ROM) type is conducted first and then serial average of Reuss type is conducted. The first ROM style average in regions with label E gives:

$$E_{x(E)} = \{ b_T E_T + (E_L + E_m) b_F/2 \} / (b_F + b_T) \quad \text{where suffix } x \text{ denotes the } x \text{ direction.} \quad (7)$$

In the regions AF, BF, CF, and DF, and also AG, BG, CG, and DG, the same procedure gives:

$$E_{x(F)} = \{ (b_F + b_T) E_T + b_F E_L + b_T E_m \} / \{ 2(b_F + b_T) \} \quad (8)$$

$$E_{x(G)} = \{ b_F E_L + (b_F + 2b_T) E_m \} / \{ 2(b_F + b_T) \} \quad (9)$$

By connecting these three moduli in Reuss estimate style, we have an approximate modulus:

$$E_{x1} = 2(b_F + b_T) / (b_T/E_{x(E)} + 2b_F/E_{x(F)} + b_T/E_{x(G)}) \quad \text{where suffix 1 denotes PSA solution.} \quad (10)$$

The second procedure is referred to as the Serial-Parallel approach (SPA) where the order of average is reversed. For example, serial linkage is counted first in regions with labels A to D as:

$$E_{x(A)} = 2(b_F + b_T) / \{ b_T/E_T + (2b_F + b_T)/E_m \}, \quad E_{x(B)} = E_L \quad (11)$$

$$E_{x(C)} = 2(b_F + b_T) / \{ (2b_F + b_T)/E_T + b_T/E_m \}, \quad E_{x(D)} = (b_F + b_T) / (b_F/E_T + b_T/E_m) \quad (12)$$

Finally, the total average of the modulus in the x-direction, denoted by E_{x2} , is obtained by ROM:

$$E_{x2} = (b_T E_{x(A)} + b_F E_{x(B)} + b_T E_{x(C)} + b_F E_{x(D)}) / \{ 2(b_F + b_T) \} \quad (13)$$

Thus, two approximating closed-form formulae are obtained.

In the previous section, only a little discussion about in-plane shear modulus, G_{LT} , was given and discussion about coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) was skipped. Because solutions for these properties are also key purpose of the present paper, they will be given below only for the PSA case. Equations for in plane shear modulus can be written as follows for the ROM part:

$$G_{xy(E)} = \{ b_T G_{TT} + (G_{LT} + G_m) b_F / 2 \} / (b_F + b_T) \quad (14)$$

$$G_{xy(F)} = \{ (2b_F + b_T) G_{LT} + b_T G_m \} / \{ 2(b_F + b_T) \} \quad (15)$$

$$G_{xy(G)} = \{ b_F G_{LT} + (b_F + 2b_T) G_m \} / \{ 2(b_F + b_T) \} \quad (16)$$

where G_{TT} denotes transverse shear modulus of the constituent UD composite bricks.

Overall averaged in-plane shear modulus by the PSA procedure, G_{xyI} , is obtained as:

$$G_{xyI} = 2(b_F + b_T) / (b_T / G_{xy(E)} + 2b_F / G_{xy(F)} + b_T / G_{xy(G)}) \quad (17)$$

For calculating CTE, a concept of a modulus modified ROM average should be introduced instead of common ROM average in a parallel linkage. The harmonic mean, Reuss estimate, should be substituted by a simple summation of thermal deformation. If we understand these modifications, CTE in the x direction can be obtained as follows, for the first parallel linkage:

$$\alpha_{x(E)} = \{ b_T E_T \alpha_T + (E_L \alpha_L + E_m \alpha_m) b_F / 2 \} / \{ b_T E_T + (E_L + E_m) b_F / 2 \} \quad (18)$$

$$\alpha_{x(F)} = \{ (b_F + b_T) E_T \alpha_T + b_F E_L \alpha_L + b_T E_m \alpha_m \} / \{ (b_F + b_T) E_T + b_F E_L + b_T E_m \} \quad (19)$$

$$\alpha_{x(G)} = \{ b_F E_L \alpha_L + (b_F + 2b_T) E_m \alpha_m \} / \{ b_F E_L + (b_F + 2b_T) E_m \} \quad (20)$$

Overall averaged CTE in the x direction by PSA procedure, α_{xI} , is obtained as:

$$\alpha_{xI} = (\alpha_{x(E)} b_T / 2 + \alpha_{x(F)} b_F + \alpha_{x(G)} b_T / 2) / (b_F + b_T) \quad (21)$$

Thus, the aimed closed form solutions of E_x , G_{xy} , and α_x are all determined.

Some comments about α_T predictions for UD phase should be stated here. Although It is well known to us that α_T is affected by matrix Poisson's ratio^(10,5), equations in the previous section can not handle such behavior. Thus, one possible and again expedient way is to incorporate a law given in Ref.10 and a similar formula to Eq. 4) in a manner of the average where the true distance between fibers is adopted here. Although a presentation of equations and results is omitted, such formula provides reasonable α_T within a few percent error from the solution of Ref.5. So far as checked by a reliable result, such crude formulae could be practically applied.

PREDICTED RESULTS FOR 3-D FABRIC COMPOSITES AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 4 indicates a comparison between calculated and experimental elastic moduli in the x-direction for Tyranno®/Epoxy 3-D fabric composites. The objective solution here is the PSA

Fig. 4: Relationships between elastic moduli and fiber volume fraction (V_{fT})

Fig.5: Relationships between in-plane shear moduli and fiber volume fraction (V_{fT})

approximation indicated by a solid curve. Because the baseline UD moduli obtained through Eq.4) and the method of Ref.5 are very close to each other, the current plot is based on the exact solution and an indication of PSA based on Eq.4) is omitted. It can be observed that an agreement between the present PSA solution and the results of homogenization finite element analysis is very favorable. They also coincide with the experimental elastic modulus. Note that a brief description about experimental procedure will be given in the next section. The SPA approximate solution provides slightly lower values than those from PSA. If we consider the simplicity of the analysis and predictability, it can be concluded that the present closed form solution for prediction of 3-D fabric composites is applicable so long as E_x concerned.

The results concerning another aimed modulus, G_{xy} , are shown in Fig.5. A solid line indicates PSA solution based on the exact UD composite input. A discrepancy from the HFEA solution tends to be greater than the previous Young's modulus case. In the case of the closed form formula, one difficulty arises to predict transverse shear modulus, G_{TT} . For solving this point, a transverse Poisson's ratio is assumed to 0.5 and transverse isotropy relation is utilized. Full closed form solution based on this simplification is indicated by a chain curve, where a discrepancy from HFEA becomes much larger than exact-UD/PSA solution. However, if we consider a simplicity and easy handling, this sort of solution could be used for some purpose. It should be noted that the experimental result fall between exact-UD/PSA and HFEA curves, being closer to the latter. Exact-UD/SPA solution provides the lowest prediction among all. So, if we pursue expediency, a combination of closed form UD and SPA might be the best.

Predicted results for coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) and the experimental value are shown in Fig.6 where HFEA solution has not been obtained yet. As stated earlier, the closed form solution for UDC was the poorest in CTE case, the indicated results are for combinations of exact-UD and PSA/SPA formulae. Mutual relations between two approximations are similar to the previous modulus cases, whereas an agreement between PSA and the experimental value is again excellent.

Fig. 6: Relationships between in-plane CTE and fiber volume fraction (V_{fT})

Fig.7 Measured Results of CTE in the Y Direction by Laser Dilatometer

OUTLINES ABOUT EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Some outline descriptions about both experimental procedures of elastic modulus and CTE measurements are given here. Selected material system was Tyranno®(standard) /Epoxy (Epicote 828) woven into SCL style 3-D fabric which contains 17 and 16 layers in the x and y directions, and consolidated through an RTM method. Volume fraction values were $V_{fT} = 43.2\%$ by experiment and $V_{fu} = 59.7\%$ calculated by Eq.6 using $b_F = 1.043\text{mm}$ and $b_T = 0.5153\text{mm}$.

Coupon specimens of 140 mm in length for the x and y directions and 180 mm in length for the 45 degree direction were used for elastic moduli. Nominal width and thickness for all specimens were 12.7mm and 5mm, respectively. Strain data up to 800×10^{-6} were employed for modulus calculation. There was found little difference in the results between the x and y directions. For obtaining in plane shear modulus, Poisson's ratios in the 45 direction were measured and the following well known formula which is only valid in the x, y and 45 directions was used:

$$G_{xy} = E_{45} / \{2 (1 + \nu_{45})\} \quad (22)$$

where E_{45} is a moduli measured for these 45 degree specimens. Average values of 5 specimen data were calculated and plotted in Figs. 4 and 5.

Coefficients of thermal expansion were measured by a dilatometer using laser interferometry whose pictures are indicated in the other paper in this conference volume¹¹⁾. A specimen which cut out of the source plate was a short block and its ends were ground to be round for a point contact.

A typical example of the measured data in the y-direction is shown in Fig.7 where the data for the second and third measurements are chosen for avoiding hygroscopic effect. An average at 25°C was adopted for an indication in Fig.6.

CONCLUSIONS

It can be mentioned that the present closed form solution in the second estimation phase of 3-D fabric composite properties, particularly PSA approach, provides excellent predictions of in-plane Young's modulus in spite of its simplicity if the elastic moduli of the constituent UD composite are properly estimated. Its reliability is confirmed by agreements with homogenization finite element predictions and experimentally obtained modulus. In-plane shear modulus by the PSA equation also shows a good agreement with HFEA and experimental results if the exact UD moduli are available. In the case of coefficient of thermal expansion, again the PSA solution provides good predictions only if the result of UD prediction phase is reliable. Thus, the main aim of the present paper to develop closed form formulae for predicting 3-D composite thermo-mechanical properties is almost fulfilled with the PSA solution.

Some imperfection in the first phase, a long-lasting classic problem of UD composite property prediction by simple closed formulae, still remains unsolved within this paper. If some expedient assumptions are allowed, a candidate equation using a logarithmic form of $a/b (= V_{fu}^{1/2})$ is proposed here for a prediction of E_T , which gives favorite curves for isotropic fiber PMCs. However, because of its expediency, the same form for G_{LT} leads to higher estimations and the equation for α_T derived based on the same idea provides much smaller values than exact calculations. Although another compromising formulae are possibly described for these two properties, persuasiveness of the concept will be degraded seriously. Thus, a conclusion about this phase is summarized as follows: A closed form solution for E_T with expedient handling of fiber distance can be formulated and it can predict a favorable value under a recognition of its limitation.

A practical goal of this research program is an application of the simple solutions to estimation of the matrix elastic modulus of CMC, which is very hard to measure. Because of the length and consistency in the discussion, description of this part is omitted in the present paper and Reference 12 should be referred for that purpose.

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